

IMPROVING THE METHODOLOGICAL SYSTEM OF PROFESSIONAL SELF-DEVELOPMENT OF FUTURE FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHERS

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Abstract: in the article, the future foreign language teachers should be provided with the latest news in their field of knowledge, their need to be aware of modern educational technologies, to be the owner of sufficient information and needs are analyzed. Public information is becoming more and more important and becoming a vital necessity. This is a legal and objective process, common to the entire world community. This process covers all aspects of human activity.

Key words: foreign language teacher, database, Interoperability, modern information educational environment, Disintermediation, educational standards, Information education.

INTRODUCTION

Complexity of information products and services. Information products in the form of software tools, data storage and storage, operational services and expert support have a tendency of constant development and increasing complexity. At the same time, the interface part of information and communication technologies eases any complexities of solving tasks based on the facilitation of interactive interaction between systems and users. Interoperability. Computer information systems, optimal exchange of data between systems and users, data transfer and formation of necessary information occupy the status of leading technological problems. Disintermediation.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Interoperability, in turn, facilitates the delivery of information products to users[2]. Unfortunately, today, graduates of higher education institutions, especially future foreign language teachers, are not sufficiently prepared to create an information environment in general secondary schools, to work in an information environment. Especially when working in the Internet education system, teachers face the following psychological and pedagogical problems[3]:

problems related to the lack of teaching theory in modern information-educational environments. It is noted that none of the existing teaching theories can be effectively used in the virtual educational environment. Attempts to organize computer or Internet education in compatibility with traditional educational methodology are not highly effective;

problems related to the optimization of the content of educational and methodical works for effective teaching process in the modern information educational environment. The problem is related to mutual coordination of educational and methodical work and various forms of information transfer to increase the effectiveness of teaching;

problems related to ensuring acceptability: presentation of educational material in accordance with psychological and ergonomic requirements, perception of educational materials presented in electronic form, ability to understand electronic material. This

problem is related to the psychological-linguistic peculiarities of students' perception of the educational material on the computer screen;

problems related to the adaptation of educators and learners to the modern information-educational environment. Solving this problem requires regular preparation of educational subjects for information technologies and modern information-educational environment;

problems related to the field of education related to limiting the regular communication of the participants of the educational process;

valeological problems. Valeology is the science of health and human health. Currently, improving the basics of a healthy lifestyle is an integral part of the theory of health care and reflects the forms and methods of organizing a person's daily life activities based on cultural norms and values;

problems related to the quality of educational materials in accordance with educational standards. The latest innovations, innovation and modernization processes in the educational process require the higher education system to prepare teaching staff for general secondary schools. Therefore, today, coherence and continuity between the types of education should be determined not only from the point of view of the problems of DTS or qualification requirements, but also from the point of view of the professional training of pedagogic personnel. Students of a higher educational institution of pedagogy, i.e. future teachers, have the following knowledge, skills, qualifications and competencies required to perform didactic tasks in order to achieve educational goals based on modern information technology tools. should do[4]:

- know the principles of information storage, processing, distribution and display;
- knowing computer and communication tools, their characteristics;
- use of the Internet in the educational process and scientific research;
- to know the methodology of using computer and communication technologies in the educational process;
- to know and use the main types of software;
- use of tools for preparation of special presentations and electronic resources;
- application of information technologies in solving practical problems in the educational process;
- creation and use of distance education electronic educational-methodical base.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

It is necessary to introduce a systematic approach to creating an informational educational environment. At the initial stage of this approach, the purpose of the information-educational environment of the educational institution is determined in accordance with the content of modern education. In pedagogical activity, the goal of education performs a systematizing task. It is the defined goal that serves as the basis for choosing the content, purpose, and organizational forms of education. The goal of modern education is the system of knowledge, skills and qualifications formed in accordance with the requirements of the specialist model, which is reflected in the relevant educational standards. In addition, according to the requirements of the national model of personnel training of our republic, the student is becoming not only the object of the pedagogical process, but also its subject. In such cases, the importance of the student's independent education increases and the formation of the following skills and qualifications is required[5];

- planning skills and qualifications for independent education: making a personal plan for independent activities; perform purposeful activities based on the plan, monitor one's own activities and make necessary adjustments to it.
- skills and abilities to use the Internet, scientific and educational information:
- independent determination of scientific and educational information;
- ability to independently analyze and evaluate new information;
- search and find information sources on the Internet in terms of the problem to be solved;
- to see new and promising news in the content of the received information.
- skills and qualifications for working on electronic information-educational resources:
- systematic use of electronic manuals and catalogs;
- being able to maintain a list of scientific, educational and other literature obtained from the Internet based on the rules of bibliography.
- skills and abilities to master lectures presented through modern information technology tools: determining the topic and plan of lectures, list of literature;
- correct acceptance of the provided information;
- to be able to distinguish the main problem and ideas and conclusions;

CONCLUSION

➤ Based on this basis, it can be said that in the development of the media culture of future foreign language teachers, the integrated cooperation of educational systems is of decisive importance, and it is necessary for the effective use of innovative organizational forms that allow obtaining new educational results. young teachers should have the skills to apply these forms of teaching based on a creative approach. Because a future foreign language teacher working in general secondary schools, or in the words of the modern era, a modern teacher, through creative thinking, individual and group counseling, including e-mail counseling it is necessary to conduct, organize educational forums, trainings, conduct computer tests, organize collective interaction of teachers and students to support the individual educational trajectory of students it is necessary to have skills.

- In the use of computer technologies (computer literacy).
- the teacher can perform several tasks according to its content. They perform the following main didactic functions:
- develops students' interest in science through the use of multimedia technologies.
- in this, due to the interactivity of education, the thinking skills of students are activated and the efficiency of learning the learning material increases.
- It is important to demonstrate real situations or to model and visualize complex processes.
- it is considered effective not only according to the level of mastery of educational material, but also according to the level of logical achievement of students.
- distance education is not organized only for self-taught students or for Internet education. It may also provide an opportunity to organize for students who have missed classes without reason.
- provides an opportunity for students to find materials for independent research and to perform certain research works by answering problematic issues.

Creates conditions for students to master a new topic, solve examples, write an essay, statement, independently familiarize themselves with educational materials, analyze information and data quickly.

one of the main features of the improvement of the educational system is the increase of the supporting information that is constantly referred to in the process of communication with the computer, the creation of an information base at a level that can meet the requirements of the computer information environment and modern times, imitation in hypertext and multimedia teaching, communication systems are adopted.

The term "database" refers to the introduction, systematization, storage and use of information with the help of computer technology.

For the traditional processing of a number of information, there are standard forms of their preparation, which include bibliography, statistical data, abstracts. The database accepts statistical, textual, graphic and visual information in an unlimited amount and, of course, in specified forms.

The knowledge base is a closed system without the need for additional information on this topic, and each of its elements will have an informed system for access to other elements that are logically connected. In this case, it is not included in the knowledge base, that is, it will not be possible to refer to external elements from it. Various encyclopedias and dictionaries serve as primary bibliographic analogies of the knowledge base.

When studying the current state of innovative training of teachers in practice, it was found that most of today's foreign language teachers and future foreign language teachers are not aware of the essence of innovative pedagogical technology, the theory of introducing innovations into the educational process, and methods of updating their activities and It was found that they don't know the tools, organize experimental tests for them in the process of education, skills are not formed enough. Therefore, today's and tomorrow's foreign language teachers should have a deep understanding of their preparation for innovative activities, have sufficient competence, and become competent teachers by improving their knowledge, skills, and abilities. In the conditions of the globalization of education, adapting the activities of teachers to the requirements of the time, creating working conditions based on competition between them, which in turn ensures that future foreign language teachers become highly competent teachers. It is possible to improve the quality of education by directing young people to innovative activities in all educational institutions, including teacher training universities. In preparing future foreign language teachers for innovative activities, it is important to increase the psychological preparation and interest of pedagogues and direct them to demonstrate their personal competence. Today, the pedagogical competence of the older generation is of great importance in the formation of the competence of future foreign language teachers. In our republic, like medical workers, many pedagogues and professors perform their profession with high competence. The deontological culture of the teacher is social pedagogical education formed in the system of continuous professional and pedagogical education. In its essence, it is the result of morally oriented education of the teacher through the requirements of professional pedagogical duty and is manifested in behavior and professional activity. It is determined by the content of professional ethical standards, moral obligation, moral ideas, humanitarian values of pedagogical activity in a multinational society. It is directed to the improvement of the methodical system of the teacher and the principles of cooperation between students, effective joint activities, and the formation of the methodical system of the future teacher. The professional competence of future foreign language teachers must meet the requirements of the world standard and the educational standard of Uzbekistan. It is necessary for a foreign language teacher to be creative, enterprising, self-

sacrificing executor of his profession, to be able to effectively use effective methods and tools based on creativity. Today's pedagogue should organize his professional activities on the basis of deontological requirements and pay attention to the upbringing of a mature generation, relying on his competence. A high sense of the teacher's duty governs the teacher's right to regulate his actions. As an important component of the professional training of future foreign language teachers, a number of scientific researches are being conducted to clarify the didactic aspects of the formation of deontological competence, to improve the pedagogical mechanism of developing methodological knowledge as the basis of innovative activity. Therefore, today's and tomorrow's foreign language teachers should try to master the secrets of professional competence. Only then will the field of education progress.

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